

Disease brief_ *Echinococcus granulosus*

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Echinococcosis is a disease that affects domestic and wild animals as well as humans. It is caused by parasitic cestodes of the genus <i>Echinococcus</i> which belongs to the family <i>Taeniidae</i>. Carnivores (Canidae) are definitive hosts while several species, among them humans, can act as intermediate hosts.</p> <p><i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> has a rural cycle usually involving dogs (as definitive hosts) and domestic animals (ruminants, pig) as intermediate hosts (Cystic Echinococcosis, CE). Wild carnivores (foxes, racoon dogs, and wolves) can act as definitive hosts.</p> <p>Humans are infected through ingestion of parasite eggs of <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> through contaminated food, water or soil, or after direct contact with animal hosts and develop Cystic echinococcosis, also known as hydatid disease or hydatidosis. This disease is often expensive and complicated to treat and may require extensive surgery and/or prolonged drug therapy (1).</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>Echinococcosis is a disease that is listed in the WOAHA Terrestrial Animal Health Code and must be reported by Member Countries and Territories according to the WOAHA Code.</p> <p><i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> is included in Dir 2003/99/EC.</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p><i>E. granulosus</i> is distributed worldwide. See ECDC for human cases distribution (2).</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>Definitive hosts of <i>E. granulosus</i> are typically canid species especially dogs (<i>Canis familiaris</i>) and several genera of domestic ungulates serve as intermediate hosts. Humans can also be infected by <i>E. granulosus</i> as an aberrant intermediate host.</p>
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	<p>For <i>E. granulosus</i> large canids (Dog, Wolf), are definitive hosts; ungulates (small ruminants, cattle, wild boar, roe deer, but locally, ungulate species may vary) are intermediate hosts.</p>
6	Vector-borne transmission	No.

7	Environmental transmission	Environmental transmission through eggs (oncospheres) shed by definitive hosts and accidentally ingested by intermediate hosts.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Through accidental ingestion of oncospheres that can contaminate food or water.
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Through accidental ingestion of oncospheres that can contaminate food or present on the fur of domestic or wild definitive hosts.
10	Disease indicators	Cystic echinococcosis in domestic ruminants and pigs at slaughter.
11	a) Clinical signs	<p>In definitive hosts there are usually no clinical signs.</p> <p><i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> causes cystic echinococcosis in intermediate and aberrant hosts.</p> <p>In intermediate hosts, signs are represented by enlargement of the abdomen, increased total body weight (due to metacestode proliferation), but loss of total body mass, weakness apathy, anorexia, ascites, intensive cellular infiltration of the liver, peritoneal cavity, other abdominal organs, and sometimes of the lungs with metacestode tissue, and finally death.</p> <p>In humans it represents a severe disease which is often lethal if left untreated. Clinical signs in humans include also cholestatic jaundice and/or epigastric pain, fatigue, weight loss, hepatomegaly.</p>
12	b) Seroconversion	In humans, serology can help in diagnosis.
13	c) Other disease indicators	In humans, imaging techniques, such as CT scans, ultrasonography, and MRIs, are used to detect cysts. After a cyst has been detected, serologic tests can confirm the diagnosis.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	None.
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	<p>In definitive hosts:</p> <p>Intestinal scraping technique (IST) can used to detect <i>Echinococcus</i> in the intestine of definitive hosts as previously described in WHO/OIE manual on</p>

		<p>Echinococcosis (9). Alternatively, the sedimentation and counting technique can be used which is more laborious but may also be more sensitive.</p> <p>For the differentiation and identification of eggs and worm fragments PCR can be used.</p> <p>Coproantigen ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) or copro ELISA provides an alternative method for diagnosing canine echinococcosis, and both polyclonal and monoclonal antibodies have been used, directed against either somatic or excretory/secretory (ES) antigens. However, tests are generally not available on a commercial basis and are developed within individual research laboratories.</p> <p>In intermediate hosts:</p> <p>Identification of cystic echinococcosis in domestic ruminants and pigs by trained meat inspectors at slaughter.</p>
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adult parasite detection in domestic dogs - at veterinary clinics to detect the adult parasite (coprological, PCR) <i>E. granulosus</i>. Case finding for elimination of the parasite from the host and eradication programs. 2. Adult parasite detection in wild canids: Convenience sampling of hunted, trapped, road killed and found dead wild canids (wolf, fox, racoon dog) to identify animals infested with adult parasites (intestinal scraping, coprological tests, PCR) <i>E. granulosus</i>. Detection of the introduction of the parasite into new areas and to detect signals for changing patterns and trends over time. <p><i>Echinococcus</i> spp. may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by <i>Echinococcus</i> spp. (diagnosis includes direct detection of pathogen), classified according of their conservation status according (International Union for the Conservation of Nature), 33,3% species are "Near Threatened", 40% are "Vulnerable", 10% Endangered, and 16,7% Critically Endangered (CR) (3).</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
Non vector-borne diseases									
Echinococcus granulosus	Ruminants								Surveillance component not eligible for funding (focus on food safety)
	Wild ruminants								No surveillance component specifically designed
	Dogs								Adult parasite detection in domestic dogs
	Wild canids								Adult parasite detection in wild canids
	Human								Surveillance components targeting human were not in scope
17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>All surveillance components aim to find cases. They all use biased (non-random, non-representative) samples of the population. Sample prevalence (the proportion of the sample that tested positive) must be interpreted with caution as it is a biased estimation of the population prevalence.</p> <p>If the date and location of samples is recorded, and the sampling frequency is relatively constant over time, in terms of the location and number of samples, they may be used to identify the introduction of the parasite into new geographic regions and they may be used to identify signals for changing patterns or trends in the population. Because the samples are biased, caution must be taken when interpreting signals, and all signals should be verified with disease investigations or other studies.</p> <p>A relevant component not included in this brief is the identification of larval stages in domestic ruminants and pigs at slaughter. This activity can be used for case finding and identification of farms where the parasites is present for on-farm disease control and for eradication programs. This is however considered out of scope for the initiative "CP-g-22-04.01 Direct grants to Member States' authorities", which does not fund activities focused on food safety and prevention of foodborne zoonosis.</p>							

18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	All EU Member States
19	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/echinococcosis2) http://atlas.ecdc.europa.eu/public/index.aspx?Dataset=27&HealthTopic=183) ENETWILD-consortium, Klaas, Marina, Sebastian, Mario, Ferroglio, Ezio, Goncalves, Catarina, Vada, Rachele, Vicente, Joaquín, Zanet, Stefania, Dolores-Gavier-Widén, Vicente, Joaquín. 2022. A review of endangered wildlife hosts in Europe for selected pathogens to be targeted by One Health surveillance. EFSA Supporting publication 2022: 19(12):EN-7766. 12 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-77664) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2021-zoonoses-report5) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2021-zoonoses-report6) Otero-Abad B., Torgerson P.R.A (2013) Systematic Review of the Epidemiology of Echinococcosis in Domestic and Wild Animals Plos Neglected Tropical Diseases https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.00022497) Woolsey I.D., Miller (2021) Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato and Echinococcus multilocularis: a review. Research in Veterinary Science 135:517-522 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rvsc.2020.11.0108) Trachsel, D., Deplazes, P., & Mathis, A. (2007). Identification of taeniid eggs in the faeces from carnivores based on multiplex PCR using targets in mitochondrial DNA. Parasitology, 134(6), 911-920.9) Eckert, J., Gemmell, M. A., Meslin, F. X., Pawlowski, Z. S., & World Health Organization. (2001). WHO/OIE manual on echinococcosis in humans and animals: a public health problem of global concern. World Organisation for Animal Health